

JURISPRUDENCE

DISCUSSING "ICEBERGS OF MORALITY"

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*"Greatness is where there is a great crime"
Nietzsche*

Abstract

"Nobody knows how many millennia morality has existed. It is known that it appeared long before the appearance of law, philosophy, sciences, aesthetics and other values of public life, that could somehow regulate life".[1.1]

Against the background of contemporary historical events, we realize, that we live in an age where morality has less importance. Nuclear catastrophes have caused concern for humanity. Confused by "lack of existence", a human being is focused on material well-being. According to Oswald Spengler, morality is "a searchable one" in such conditions. Even today, in the infinite space of morality, we try to find out what is the ultimate purpose of our existence. Accordingly, we meet "the existing icebergs" and at the same time, in order to explain human moral behavior, we try to understand the "essence of evil and good".

It is known, that we evaluate our own actions either positively or negatively. From the point of view of morality, these actions have their own logical scheme and the mentioned scheme carries its mental content.

The question is as follows:

To what extent it is possible to determine the complex layers of personal morality by using the logic scheme of morality, which is based on the data that an individual "possesses" (consciously or unconsciously) about himself.

In the process of discussing this wide-ranging issue, we will have to "overcome some obstacles". Nikolai Berdyaev makes the following remark about the main dilemma: "The secret of an individual, his individuality can not be fully understood by anyone. The human personality is more mysterious than the world." Human being is the whole world, individ is a microcosm, which combines everything in itself. However, everything is distinctly actualized and shaped in his personality, which is individually special." [1. 90]

The approximate model of the algorithm of morality is focused on the proper recognition and understanding of what is "individually special" in an individual, that is, what is "distinctly actualized and shaped". (at least to some extent!). We try to establish the structure of the above mentioned model and we believe, that it is quite possible to implement it in both organizational and judicial practices.

In our opinion, the probable model of the algorithm of morality, its form and content will help us to open and present the "inner currents" of the world of personal morality; In any case, both the judicious management and use of its mechanism will help us to identify the reasons and the primary sources determining "the individ's good and evil behaviors", which crack "innocent" morals of human being and drive them to commit crimes. In other words, the purpose of using the moral algorithm is to study both the contradictions and hidden reasons in a human being, which provoke the legal consciousness to commit a crime in order to restore justice. We look for existential manifestations of both morality and immorality exactly within these boundaries.

Keywords: Kindness, Evil, Justice, Injustice, Crime, Morality, Algorithm of Morality.

The study of the essence, nature, foundations and principles of morality is essential for philosophical-legal thinking. The question of morality in philosophy and jurisprudence is based on an in-depth analysis of moral-legal categories of evil and good, fault, crime, punishment and other similar content.

One of the most important answers to the question of what is evil, is the following: "Evil is not a concept, it is a name of a threat that can be faced by free consciousness".[3. 1] We consider the presence of evil in

the criminal act - evil - as a permanent possibility of crime, inspired by free consciousness, which represents a real threat to free consciousness.

In our research, we discuss both the existence and use of the approximate model of the algorithm of morality. In order to understand the possibility and expediency of its practical use, we should discuss the basic approaches of moral philosophy in relation to such fundamental issues as understanding the essence of human freedom, "good and evil, blame and crime, punishment

and other moral-legal categories". In our opinion, the theoretical analysis of the presented issues will help us to establish the structure of the algorithm of morality as well as "determine the limits of its legal application".

As we have already mentioned, the existence of crime as a legal fact is considered and evaluated in relation to the categories of justice and injustice. The use of the moral algorithm also provides for the promotion of litigation practice. We think that in order to determine human behavior (moral and immoral), actions, causes and consequences (just and unjust) with more objectivity in the process of studying and evaluating legal facts, the use of the moral algorithm in legal proceedings will become more effective mechanism and means of making fair decisions.

The Theoretical Part.

The classical period of the transcendental foundations of moral categories is the ancient Socratic-Platonic philosophy, where "true knowledge" is given only by the knowledge of eternal ideas, the basis of which is the basis of knowledge and the purpose of knowledge is to determine the meaning of the concept, that is, "knowledge of knowledge".

Accordingly, the way of forming human's own "self" is based on "the transition period from ignorance to knowledge"; A man moves into eternal world of ideas through self-awareness, where he rises and finds "his own being". A man equipped with knowledge is in communion with the supreme truth in the ascension of the soul; According to the opinion, that "the limit of the world accessible to the mind is the idea of goodness,...in the visible world it gives birth to light".[4.124] A man charged with both intelligence and the idea of goodness is successful in both private and public lives. Knowledge is the guarantee of good behavior as for ignorance, it is the main cause of moral failure. Evil is the result of ignorance of good, that is, the fact of spiritual weakness, revealing both strong human inclinations towards "wrongdoing and high risk of falling". Aristotle's study of the issue of morality is connected to the empirical study of human nature. In the polemic with the great teacher, he discusses his own opinion in a practical direction.

According to sage of stagiaire, the causes of personal crime are in their real lives, that is, in the mutual relations of citizens; In his political-legal philosophy, there are three types of relations related to the "good of others": distributive, commutative and retributive ones. We should look for the basis of crime in this reality - "in the unjust acts, caused by the distribution of the most important goods of life." According to the philosopher, the cause of conflict between citizens is related to the unequal distribution of burdens and benefits, and "the savior of the state is the principle of reciprocity", which is based on involuntary (forced) exchange. "Such exchanges are carried out secretly - for example, theft, fornication, intoxication, matchmaking, slave recruitment, secret murder, perjury - or coercion - for example, humiliation, capture, killing, robbery, mutilation, cursing, humiliation".[5.71]

Only one individual acts in case of retributive justice. "He repays another person with good and evil behavior for good and evil actions, committed by him.

The above mentioned actions can be both real and imaginary ones. A form of partial justice can be gratitude, revenge, or punishment.

According to Kashnikov's fair opinion, the justice based on Aristotle is the part of the law that is "represented in the activity of justice, starting from Talion, whose demand was "an eye for a share of a stable, a tooth for a share of a tooth", and ending with modern criminal and civil proceedings".[5.72]

While evaluating crime, evil, goodness and other ethical problems, we encounter different approaches in the philosophical and theological thinking of the Middle Ages. In moral themes, ideological changes cause changes in legal approaches. The reason for this is the following: the legal indicator of morality is the free will of a person.

What is evil - evil is "the lack of good", that comes from the lack of being. "The lack of presence is also a sin, the result of arbitrary departure from God. By blind obedience to free will, "...sin leads to a loss of orientation," which provides the basis for moral crime. There is no punishment for this sin, the sin itself is the punishment: the dramatic impoverishment of the human being".[3.41]

So what's the solution to the problem? Is there a transcendental basis of human's free will, that will protect us from sin in the conflict between good and evil? - **This is God**, says blessed Augustine.

We must consider, that in medieval theology, human's free will has not found a center of personal dignity. The individual does not have "a moral courage" to defend himself against sin and evil behavior. The Blessed One's request to God is as follows: "The house of my soul is narrow... so expand it. If it breaks down: repair it". [6.5]

An African theologian has experienced the misfortune of history on the example of his own city. He is convinced that the danger of destruction, except the "city of God", constantly follows even "terrestrial city". Moreover, there is a great gap between them, as there are "empty boxes" between faith and knowledge. Finally, all the above reasoning points show us that we have the least chance to get justice in human history. This is the only place where a frustrated and battle-scarred man's soul can find inner peace. This is the only place where space is "open" for both moral and legal judgments.

In moral philosophy, as in almost every sphere of public life, the XVI-XVII centuries are distinguished by special changes. "In philosophical-legal thinking, the essence of changes was revealed... by concentrating on the individual, which meant that from that period it became necessary for a man: to understand unconventional ontological status of one's existence, to establish new conceptual boundaries with the world and identify ideological foundations". [5.99]

During the Renaissance era, in the contents of consciousness, the changes were revealed by an extremely cruel approach: "A man is a wolf to a man." Another significant statement by Thomas Hobbes is as follows: "Man's life is a true solitude, a poverty, a bitterness, an animality and it is short."

The presented opinion allows us to realize the fact that in relation to time, ("opposed to time"), the consciousness finds its own strength to cope with the existing conditions. From this point of view, it wants and at the same time it "is obliged" to survive even through power and violence, because on this path, everyone has their own interests and the existing conflict must be overcome in any case, as historically, "there is a war of all against all" between people.

In such a situation, we can have the most relevant question: what is the mechanism that protects a man, his identity? - The English philosopher's answer to the above mentioned question is as follows: "This mechanism is: **the State, that is, a Mortal God**". According to Thomas Hobbes, the state is a Mortal God governed by the social contract. The public contract has another important burden - it sets the limits of human freedom. According to Hobbes: "it is necessary to regulate public relations on the basis of contract. The reason for this is not the opinion that human nature is "evil". The only reason is that "a man is "free" by nature". Considering the above mentioned opinions and legal significance of the Law, the internal relations are subject to the moral law and "...when changing the contract, no person should ask to get any kind of right that can cause any kind of damage to another person. [8.107]

According to the teachings of John Locke, the possibility of breaking the social contract was revealed, not with the idea of gaining individual freedom of the person, but with the demand to get both the freedom of the society and the rights to the common goods. The legal role of the state is strong in terms of protection of rights, and in case of their violation, the state has the obligation to charge and punish the offender. The state has the following rights: to protect "Human life, liberty and property of a person".

According to the interest of our research, we would like to discuss another important nuance presented by the English philosopher. He says: "In order to protect all mankind, all men can restrain, and if necessary destroy, those who threaten the peace and security of the human race. That is, a person can cause such harm to a violator of the law, which makes the criminal repent of his crime. This example will make other people refrain from committing the same crime. According to the above mentioned opinions, every person has a right to punish the criminal and become the executor of the natural law". [9.271. Encroachment on the life of the offender is permissible if the reason for the aforementioned situation was caused by theft, as a result of which the person had lost his property. Locke shares Jean-Jacques Rousseau's opinion regarding the causes of crime. According to the philosophers, the "inner currents" of civil life force "a naturally good person" to commit evil behavior.

Locke has an unequally important attitude towards property. As for Rousseau's attitude, it depends on the negatives obtained from civilization. According to both thinkers: the state and the law are moral and legal means, which can regulate the human order. Enmity can be eliminated only on the basis of the unity of the individual and the state.

Kant has different opinion about "the essence of freedom, good-evil, guilt, crime and punishment". He thinks that a person with **evil tendencies** is protected by his conscience, that is, his moral duty. Morality is the sublime mystery of the universe. Crime and related moral-legal attributes are expected outcomes based on free will of a person.

Kant is a great representative of the Enlightenment era. Here are clearly defined the gaps and contradictions of the mind as well as their main role in a real life. "A person who is not wise, can not be a master in his own house". [3.143]. This is an epochal approach to human beings.

But there is another question: What will be the basis for a mind freed from dogmas? Within the framework of morality, a mind freed from dogmas has decided to establish a new hierarchical order. Considering this aspect, Kant's rationalization of the world requires new creative powers of free mind.

This becomes especially important against the background, when the opinions of Kant's predecessors about the "aimless chaos of matter" and its "aimlessly playful nature" are known to everyone. That's why in Königsbergel's philosophical works, religion is no longer the basis of morality and it seeks its own foundations in human morality.

Such an approach is logical for the age of enlightenment. Another question is the extent to which human moral powers can prevent the existence of evil. In other words to what extent they can make morality capable and effective.

All-seeing Kant" leaves us face to face with the decisions which are morally strong (though hard to follow!) Evil is "an inclination" accompanying human free will, but it is not "coercion"! This view is a cornerstone of Kant's moral philosophy: under conditions of practical mind control of "Maxims" action, a man, as a rational being with free will, always has an opportunity to give the right direction to his behavior and win over evil.

In moral philosophy, the main thesis of the categorical imperative is imbued with the following pathos: "Do as you have always treated mankind in your own form and in the form of all others, treat it as an aim and not as a mere means." [10.157] This is an arena of Kantian freedom. It is quite difficult to pass it. It is autonomous, loaded with categorical requirements, but at the same time it is "creatively filled and morally actualized". A person obeys the law by his own action - he implements a mandatory rule of conduct chosen by him. The free mind of man relies on the categorical imperative, which is a strict regulator of a man's behavior;

Categorical imperative is an unconditional demand for an individual's action, which "forces" the individual to make decent decisions on the basis of his moral choice. At the same time is a man's moral guarantor. This is completely different from the rule determined by a man's own mind. To what extent is it in line with the interests of others?

The German genius knows this dead end well. That's why the philosopher has a special attitude to the law. According to Kant, in the great war of interests between men, the only restraining force against moral

misconduct is the law. In any historical era, including modern times, the existence of "a wide world of crime" calls into question Kant's moral credo -ability to implement high moral requirements. The moral law, the ideal "orientation" of the human world, is always accompanied by difficulties, fulfilling their functions. This situation is related to human's "lack of existence".

We will finish our discussion on the sense of crime with the words of the great Russian existentialist N. Berdyaev :

I will never say that a person who falls out of the universal moral law is an unhappy and condemned one. I want to declare that the guardian of universal moral law, a completely immoral person, is a candidate for hell, and a person condemned by moral laws is a moral person, who showed the sacred obligation of lawlessness". [1.43] It is an interesting but unusual application. The philosopher puzzles us and confirms his worldview once again with the following words: "I really feel an antipathy towards both winners and successful people. For me, it's an adjustment to a world that lives in evil." [1.21]

It is clear that the philosopher discusses the morality of "an innocent offender". He examines the morality of the hero who fights the continuous icebergs of morality on his own and he knows that there is less chance of victory. Yes, these are the icebergs that are sometimes surmountable, but in most cases they threaten to destroy the human world. The Russia-Ukraine war of 2022-2023 is an accurate reflection of this reality.

We are well familiar with the heroes of the Georgian genius, Vazha Pshavela. These heroes also confront the recognized tradition of law and eventually they die morally and physically. The Great Creator appreciates the sacrifices made by "innocent criminals". He says: "sometimes the law goes beyond the law!" The legal mind evaluates goodness, justice, guilt, punishment, evil, transgressions and leaves the person and his morality in a dead end.

Our attempt to construct a morality algorithm is focused on overcoming moral and legal contradictions. We believe, that his involvement in the proceedings will contribute to the establishment of justice in real life.

Conclusion. In the presented work, we tried to highlight the dark and bright sides of human morality. We presented the difficulties and discussed ways to overcome them. We talked about the existence of a probable model of the algorithm of morality, we discussed the real possibility of using a new mechanism in

judicial decisions. We believe, that the approximate model of the moral algorithm may become a useful mechanism in the process of legal evaluation of the crime. On the one hand it will help the judge "to measure" the moral indicators of "an innocent offender" and on the other hand, it will help establish both innovative moral and legal regulations "in the name of justice". The purpose of its use is to promote judicial practice. Finally, "recognition and use of the algorithm of morality with legal significance ... also **considers** an attempt to obtain "a right of admission" of morality in law". [10.258] .We will discuss the above mentioned issues together with the topics of similar importance in more detail in the next studies.

References

1. Source: <https://www.scribd.com/read/454800218/> N. Berdiev, self-awareness-part-I, p. 90;
2. A. Nikitich, Ethics. "Fair Georgia", 2015, p. 192;
3. Rüdiger Safranski, The Drama of Evil or Freedom. Ilia State University Publishing House, Tbilisi, 2015, pp. 1-43;
4. Plato, State. Introduction to Modern Thought, Part I Ilia State University Publishing House, Tbilisi, 2009, p. 124;
5. Salome Khizanishvili, Irakli Gabisonia, Aleksandre Taliashvili. Justice - philosophical-legal aspects. "Universal" publishing house, Tbilisi, 2019, p. 71;
6. Blessed Augustine, Confessor. Publishing House of Tbilisi Independent University "Neker", 1996, p. 5;
7. Hobbes T. Leviathan, or Matter, form and power of the church and civil state. Ch. I: About a person. Ch. XV // Hobbes T. Leviathan. M.: Thought, 2001. S. 107;
8. Source: <https://library.iliauni.edu.ge/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/jon-loki.pdf>, John Loki, Second Treatise on Civil Government", Chapter I, pp. 271-272;
9. Immanuel Kant: Critique of Practical Reason. Sat. 6 volumes, T. 3. M., 1964, art. 347.
10. Khizanishvili, S., Dzaganian, K., & Butovecky, Modernity and the Question of the Existence of Moral Probabilities. DOI:10.14738/assrj.99.13042. A. (2022). Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal, 9(9). 256-258;